

Key Facts

Duration: October 2023 – November 2026
EU Contribution: € 5.704.187,50
Programme: Horizon Europe Programme

The Consortium

Coordinator: Technological University of the Shannon:
Midlands Midwest (Ireland)

Partners: 14 leading partners in the area of Cybersecurity Defence and AI (7 academic institutions and 4 industrial partners) and 3 critical infrastructure operators.

The Challenge

From energy grids to smart factories, critical infrastructures face rising cyber threats that exploit complex, interconnected, and heterogeneous systems. Traditional security approaches often struggle to provide the situational awareness needed for effective resilience in these dispersed environments. ResilMesh's primary objective is to strengthen digital resilience by developing a cutting-edge Security Orchestration and Analytics Platform Architecture (SOAPA) toolset. This platform will integrate AI-driven detection algorithms, dynamic risk assessment forecasting, and interoperable security controls to help Computer Security Incident Response Teams (CSIRTs) anticipate attacks and respond more effectively.

The Mission

The project's mission is to improve digital infrastructure resilience through five key objectives:

- Improving end-to-end data aggregation and security control interoperability in dispersed digital infrastructures.
- Giving CSIRTs better awareness of the service and asset dependencies of their network.
- Helping CSIRTs to build cyber resilience capacity.
- Developing AI-based algorithms and tools for early and ongoing attack detection and prediction.
- Developing a situation assessment system to view and forecast network level risk.

These objectives are achieved through a 10-work package project plan that builds a SOAPA platform by combining existing security controls and tools from consortium participants with readily available open-source elements, then integrating newly developed algorithms and software.

The Impact

The ResilMesh SOAPA Platform

- AI-Enhanced Detection & Prediction: Algorithms to improve attack detection and prediction for endpoints and network traffic.
- Situation Awareness & Risk Forecasting: A system to view and forecast network-level risk while preserving privacy.
- Improved Threat Intelligence: Increasing the reliability and granularity of shared threat intelligence for better threat hunting and cyber forensics incident response.

Real-World Validation (8 Pilots)

- Three Core Use Cases:
 - Renewable Energy SCADA – Protecting critical energy infrastructure.
 - Smart Manufacturing Robotics – Securing automated industrial environments.
 - Regional Civil Infrastructure – Enhancing resilience of public systems.
- Five Open Call Use Cases: Additional pilots selected through an open call to ensure evaluation across a wide range of critical infrastructures.

Capacity Building & Best Practices

- CSIRT Empowerment: Helping CSIRTs deal with digital infrastructure complexity and heterogeneity by providing tools for better awareness of environment dependencies, threats, and risk.
- Suite of Best Practices: Providing guidance and tools to build cyber capacity and improve resilience preparation across Europe.